

Security Requirements for the Optical Transport Network from the Perspective of a Service Provider

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Abstract—Optical transport networks have revolutionized data transmission, forming the backbone of modern communications and supporting data rates exceeding 400 Gbit/s per wavelength. Due to the large volume of data transmitted on the optical network, including sensitive data from governments, banking transactions, enterprises, critical assets, etc., it is exposed to increasingly sophisticated security threats, requiring the implementation of comprehensive security measures across the network, addressing each network element and layer individually. This paper examines the vulnerabilities of the optical transport network, and provides security recommendations to protect the data in transit through a variety of traffic encryption methods and other security measures according to the level of criticality required by the use case or regulations.

Index Terms—Optical Network, Security, Encryption cards, MACsec, QKD, PQC

I. INTRODUCTION

The transport network forms the backbone of modern telecommunications, enabling the transmission of high-capacity data across potentially long distances and offering interoperability between various network elements. The transport network is continuously evolving to meet the growing demands of businesses and consumers, driven by the increasing adoption of services such as mobile technologies (LTE-A, 5G) and fixed solutions (IPTV, ultra-broadband, SME services, etc.). The telecom operator's transport network comprises several segments, including the mobile backhaul, fronthaul, and interfaces on the core network edge, which leverage various telecommunications technologies, such as microwave, optical, and IP communications. By combining different architectures, topologies, capacities and performance, users/customers can be provided with connectivity adapted to their needs. Network operators are increasingly embracing an 'open' philosophy in their transport architectures at the IP and optical layers. This involves implementing three key strategies: (a) Technology Evolution, transformation of IP and optical networks following a multiservice, multilayer flat-

tened network approach; (b) Software-Defined Networking (SDN), integration of the network into the Control Plane, which brings intelligence to the IP and optical layers; and (c) Network Disaggregation, which offers freedom of choice regarding the network equipment, without vendor dependency, leveraging compliance with open protocols, thus enhancing agility, efficiency, and service delivery. The objective of these strategies is to provide enhanced capacity while improving service quality and ensuring cost-efficiency through a higher degree of standardization. However, this approach brings new security challenges, including the introduction of new open transport protocols, architectural designs and specific security requirements for disaggregation.

A new technological risk that network operators must address is the threat posed by Cryptographically Relevant Quantum Computers (CRQC). CRQCs are powerful computing systems that operate based on quantum mechanics, and perform specific calculations exponentially faster than classical computers. This compromises traditional encryption methods, currently used to securitize digital communications for both in-transit and stored data. This new risk presented by CRQC computers is "harvest now, decrypt later", based on collecting data that are currently unreadable and storing it in the hope of being able to decrypt it in the future.

This paper presents a security approach and discusses security requirements for the optical transport network, specifically addressing the lower layers, from the physical (OTN) layer (L1) to the network layer (L3). We provide a network operator's vision, covering different levels of protection according to the level of criticality required by the scenario and/or regulations. Likewise, we also present new security measures for the medium term.

II. GENERAL SECURITY APPROACH

The telecommunications infrastructure is currently one of the critical infrastructure to be protected. Network operators

make use of fibre-optic transport technology to efficiently provide high-speed data transmission capabilities across different network environments. In order to ensure integral protection, security must be implemented by design, introducing security practices in a cross-cutting manner across all optical network layers to achieve robust protection from malicious attacks and damages. The most fundamental cybersecurity design principles [1] include: Defense-in-depth, the implementation of various security tools and procedures; Least Privilege, limit the level of access as minimum as possible to reduce security breaches; Separation of Duties, divide responsibilities between several people; Security by Default, the security of the systems are activated by default; Modularity, splitting the system into small and independent components; Secure Failure, network design to minimize impact in case of failure; and, Isolation, limiting the exposure of network elements. These principles must be enforced for a robust approach to system security. From the perspective of optical transport network security, different levels can be distinguished regarding the specific protection measures to be applied:

- **Transport network plane:** Management of transport layer infrastructure. Security measures shall be implemented for all physical elements and nodes, with a stronger focus on security depending on the criticality of the node, e.g. nodes physically located outside the operator's management network, or border nodes.
- **Control plane:** Configuration, establishment, and management of traffic flow. The security protection techniques will depend on the proprietary control protocols of each supplier. However, network equipment should always be hardened, and specific measures should be added depending on the organisation of the control plane.
- **Management plane:** Administration and monitoring of network devices. In terms of equipment and network management protection, hardening, configuration of secure protocols, access control, remote authentication, filtering, and audit, shall always be implemented. Additionally, security measures should be considered at levels 2 and 3 of the networks.
- **Service plane:** Management and delivery of end-user services. It is required to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of service traffic.

The implementation of security measures for all elements in the optical network, from the different points of view (planes) mentioned above, provides a secure network deployment. Fig. 1 depicts a simplified view of a segmented, multilayer, hierarchical optical transport network topology. It is divided into the control plane and the data plane. The control plane consists of an SDN orchestrator, and three SDN controllers: IP, optical and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). The data plane is split into the IP layer and the optical layer, and adopts the terminology defined in [2]. The network is segmented into a national domain (with IP routers belonging to hierarchical levels HL3 and HL2) and a metro-regional domain (with HL4 IP routers). Connectivity in the metro-regional domain is shown

to rely on IPoDWDM technology, while the national domain utilizes optical transponders for enhanced performance. QKD modules and Key Management Systems (KMS) are placed in the metro-regional domain, whereas encryption over dark fibre connections to customer premises is assumed to rely on Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC). Encryption throughout the national network with QKD or PQC will be possible. On the service plane, HL4-HL3 and HL3-HL2 services are assumed to use L3 encryption, while customer access lines use L2 encryption (potentially, L1 encryption, if OTN equipment is deployed on both ends of the customer lines).

Fig. 1. Simplified hierarchical optical transport network with SDN control and multilayer data plane. Shown are encrypted services relying on QKD in the metro-regional segment (HL4-HL3). PQC-based security mechanisms are assumed across customer access lines. The national segment (HL3-HL2) can be QKD or PQC.

III. GENERAL SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

In this section, we outline generic security measures that, due to their characteristics, are considered basic to ensure adequate regulatory compliance of each network element.

A. Authentication and access control

Authentication is the process of verifying the identity of a user, process, or device, often as a prerequisite to allowing access based on user roles to resources in an information system, [3]. The general security requirements to accomplish proper authentication are: 1) The Optical Network (ON) shall support segmentation by authenticating on different trusted domains, and each ON element shall be uniquely identified. 2) The device shall require strong authentication for any type of local or remote access to it, supporting integration with a Centralized Authentication Service (CAS), 3) PQC/hybrid Digital certificates must be used to verify the identity of devices. The authentication process shall verify the ON device's identity via the shared key assignment, generated with at least 16 alphanumeric characters. The sensitive material shall be stored in a protected environment (i.e. strongly encrypted, Hardware Security Module (HSM)), 4) There should be at least two types of user profiles: restricted and administrative. Policies shall be implemented based on complex password requirements, regular password updates, 5) The implemented

encryption shall be non-reversible and with a high security level, being CRQC resistant. 6) Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) is required, 7) Regular Audits and Monitoring or Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) must be implemented.

B. Data security: Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability

1) *Confidentiality protection:* All transmissions between OTN devices shall be protected by a confidentiality security association and encryption techniques following section 6 ETSI TS 103 924 [4]. For service traffic protection TLSv1.3 is recommended (including PQC in key exchange), and the encryption key shall be at least AES-256. The device shall integrate an HSM where the key is securely stored.

2) *Integrity protection:* The solution shall support protection against malicious interference and data integrity in transit, this is achieved combined with encryption. Also, it is recommended to provide a mechanism capable of detecting and alerting in case the signal has suffered a change, degradation or sudden change in behaviour.

3) *Availability protection:* Optical networks are vulnerable to conventional physical attack. For this reason, the fibre-optic infrastructure shall apply the general principles for Redundancy protection, Denial of Service (DoS) protection, Network Security awareness defined in section 8 ETSI TS 103 924. It also include backup for QKD interfaces failures. In turn, the optical devices shall have security event logging, generation of audit logs, software control and hardened according to the measures provided by the CIS [5] and NIST [6], manufacturer's documentation.

IV. SPECIFIC SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

The service's traffic encryption, which ensures the confidentiality of data in transit, can be carried out by different technologies depending on the addressed layer. Such traffic encryption will depend on the customer's needs and, can be performed on any network segment. However current technology focuses on encrypting traffic on network segments HL1 (core network), HL2 (backbone network) or HL3 (aggregation network), depending on the criticality.

A. Service Encryption: Layer 1

It is possible to introduce encryption modules to provide encryption between two ports at Optical Transport layer, Layer 1. The encryption module's card is a pluggable component designed to secure data as it travels through the optical transport network based on the ITU-T G.709.1 recommendation [7]. It provides Layer 1 traffic encryption between two ports of two devices at sites A and B based on the AES-256 protocol, ensures that the transmitted data is protected from unauthorized access maintaining confidentiality and integrity at the transport layer.

B. Service Encryption: Layer 2

It is possible to introduce encryption modules to provide encryption between two ports at Ethernet layer, Layer 2, based on Media Access Control Security (MACSec) protocol. The

specific security requirements are: 1) The available algorithm to offer protection in data transmission between source and destination (MACsec encryption algorithm) and MACSec Key Agreement (MKA) encryption algorithm shall be AES-256 or higher, 2) The CAK key shall have a length of 256 bits 3) The MACSec configuration shall be implemented in both communication-ends with the same parameters (CKN, CAK, MKA, CKN) and, 4) It is recommended to implement MACSec in equipment's located outside the security perimeter.

C. Service Encryption: Layer 3

Traffic encryption at layer 3 focuses on the encryption performance at the access level, in the Optical Terminal (OT) equipment. Each OT pair will share a single encryption key, these keys shall be distributed to the OT pair via key distribution methods such as KMS, or via secure protocols (PQC with TLS v1.3). The traffic received from the access level shall be encrypted with AES-256 security, the signal will be transmitted through the backbone network and, eventually, received by the other OT, which will decrypt the signal.

Three key elements are necessary: Key Generator Entity, system responsible for the creation, management and distribution of the encryption keys; Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), a system responsible for the SSL/TLS certificates emission; KMS, which manages and stores the cryptographic keys. Additionally, it is recommended to separate the management plane into different network environments with different subnets, and each device shall maintain direct visibility of each system that comprises the security architecture. The specific security requirements for the encryption of service traffic are: 1) The key exchange protocol shall be TLS 1.3 or similar protocols: IKEv2, QKD; 2) The symmetric generated key shall be AES-256 or higher; 3) The device shall integrate an HSM module where the cipher keys are securely stored; 4) The key exchange method must be robust; 5) Both devices (OT) that constitute the communication's endpoints shall apply the same encryption algorithm; 6) The communication with PKI, KMS, key generator entity or any network device shall use TLS 1.3; 7) The traffic's encryption shall not impact on the performance, functionality and management of such OT device.

D. Quantum-Safe (QS) Security Solutions

To achieve quantum-secure optical networks, it is necessary to integrate new Quantum Safe technologies into the network in the near-future to avoid the security risks posed by the existence of CRQC computers. There are currently two lines of work, which shall coexist and work in a hybrid mode.

1) *Post-Quantum Cryptography:* As NIST defines "The goal of post-quantum cryptography (also called quantum-resistant cryptography) is to develop cryptographic systems that are secure against both quantum and classical computers and can interoperate with existing communications protocols and networks" [8]. For the moment, this organization has approved two Digital Signature Standard algorithms (ML-DSA [9] and SLH-DSA [10]) and a Key-Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) (ML-KEM [11] and HQC [12]). The migration to

PQC, with the integration of such algorithms into current protocols and network devices, is a challenge for the industry that should be carried out gradually until we achieve QS networks. To consider L1, L2 or L3 QS traffic encryption, the KEM shall be approved by NIST or international standardization organizations, and achieve AES-256 or higher encryption. During this transition, it is recommended to establish a QS and traditional backup entity.

2) *Quantum Key Distribution*: QKD aims to solve the key generation and distribution problem. It creates a secret key between two authorized parties connected by a quantum channel and a classical authenticated channel [13]. The limitations presented by this technology are based on the quantum channel requirements, as optical fibre requires limited distance and challenges to withstand co-propagation with classical fibre-optic channels. Additionally, dedicated QKD hardware is required, and long-distance reachability shall integrate the use of secure trusted nodes. For these reasons, the integration of QKD technology as the key distribution method will make sense in specific scenarios, including physically secure locations. The Network Operator shall follow the QKD ETSI specifications, ETSI GS QKD, to obtain a secure QKD implementation.

E. SDN Security Requirements

The integration of SDN technology offers intelligence, and a homogeneous and unified control plane for IP and Optical Networks. To obtain this open architecture, the SDN and the network devices shall communicate via standardized ONF Transport API (T-API) data models and support HTTPS with TLS 1.3 transport protocol, and implement AES-256 cipher suites or higher. The T-API security requirements are the same as for a generic API. Likewise, SDN can be extended to QKD networks to seamlessly control a QKD-enabled optical network end-to-end [14]. The SDN security requirements are: 1) All entities that access the SDN-C via interfaces shall be authenticated, 2) The SDN-Cs shall support software integrity verification in installation/upgrade stage, 3) Implement an appropriate access control, following the recommendations TR-529 by Open Networking Foundations, 4) The SDN-C solution shall support RESTCONF as defined in RFC 8040 and NETCONF according to RFC 6241, 5) To prevent DoS attacks, it is required to support monitoring of the computing capacity consumption, activate the anti-DoS mechanisms when the consumption reaches the threshold, including anti-DoS from northbound/southbound interfaces, and limit the boundary of resource consumption.

F. Security Requirements depending on the Network Segment

Security measures shall be applied across the entire network, with greater emphasis at border nodes, nodes (minimum one node) with connectivity to the management network and nodes at off-site locations, e.g. lockers on the street or in customer offices. It is recommended to integrate and coexist different subnetworks for each of the different network environments and suppliers for the management plane. The security configurations shall ensure that, if any element of the solution

is compromised, the rest of the network and the service and management are not affected as far as possible.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Security shall be applied in a cross-cutting manner in all network equipment, from the layers closest to the actual physics of data transmission to the routing of packets. Operators should prioritize, as a future goal, the implementation of end-to-end security focusing on security integration at the lower layers of the optical network. This requires strong encryption, authentication, and continuous monitoring to ensure data integrity and confidentiality. Beyond the safe integration of new technologies (e.g., QKD/PQC), phasing out legacy systems helps cut costs, reduce maintenance, and enhance security.

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